

THE MAIN TASK OF TEACHING MATHEMATICS IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS

Orinbasar Saparov Bakhievish

*The National Center for Training Teachers in New Methods of the Republic of
Karakalpakstan*

Senior teacher of mathematics

Annotation: This article describes in detail the main task of teaching mathematics in secondary schools, new technical tools for teaching mathematics, and a competency-based approach to mathematics education.

Key words: mathematics, competence approach, logical method, mathematical education system.

Introduction:

In the current era, when new technical tools, including computers and other information technologies, are rapidly entering the teaching of mathematics, using the achievements of computer science in order to ensure interdisciplinary coherence is considered one of the serious issues. The introduction of computer technologies in educational institutions opens a wide way to optimize the educational process.

Literature analysis and methodology:

Competency-based approach to mathematics education implies the formation and development of practical skills that allow students to act effectively in situations encountered in their professional, personal and everyday life, as well as strengthening the practical, practical directions of mathematics education.

In order to teach mathematics to young people, a teacher must know these subjects well and be able to skillfully use teaching methods. At the same time, it is

necessary to have deep knowledge of pedagogy, psychology and other sciences. This increases the mental load in the mathematics lesson and forces the student to think about the need to increase activity and interest in the material during the lesson. Therefore, new active methods and methods of teaching are taught to activate students' thinking and express their independent knowledge.

One of the urgent issues is to use the achievements of computer science in order to ensure interdisciplinary coherence in the current era, when new technical tools, including computers and other information technologies, are rapidly entering the teaching of mathematics. The introduction of computer technologies in educational institutions opens a wide way to optimize the educational process.

Results:

Competency approach to mathematics education implies acquisition of various skills by students that enable them to act effectively in situations encountered in professional, personal and everyday life in society. Thus, in the competence-based approach, the basis of mathematical education is aimed at strengthening practical, practical directions.

When checking the knowledge of mathematics, it is necessary to take into account not only the presence of this or that knowledge in the minds of students according to the requirements of the program, but also the following that describe its quality. It is necessary to study the classification of all teaching methods in order to consciously choose among the methods of teaching the new content and new tasks of education.

The importance of mathematics education is determined by its role in the development of science and technology, in the production areas of information and communication technologies and in everyday life. In addition to training creative and creative personnel to meet economic requirements, quality education should also be provided to those who use these achievements as consumers.

Discussion:

The simplest concepts that cannot be determined conditionally are accepted in the

school mathematics course. For example, in an arithmetic course, the concept of number and addition, and in a geometry course, the concepts of plane, point, distance, and straight line are undefined concepts. Using these concepts, other mathematical concepts are defined.

A number of factors affect the implementation of the mathematical education system, as well as the general goals of education, the socialization and socialization of education, the development of mathematics as a science, the orientation of mathematics to practice, new educational ideas and technologies and results affect psychological research. The sum of these factors constitutes the external environment and it directly affects the mathematics education system. Many components of the external environment affect mathematics through the purpose of teaching it.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, it should be said that the methodology of using modern information technologies in the teaching of mathematics. In the present era, when new technical tools, including computers and other information technologies, are rapidly entering the teaching of mathematics, using the achievements of computer science in order to ensure interdisciplinary coherence is one of the urgent issues. It is also possible to use modern information technology tools in teaching mathematics, explaining its topics and organizing demonstrations.

References:

1. Jumayev M.E. Mathematics teaching methodology. Tashkent. "Turan-Iqbal". 2016.
2. A.Nurmetov, I.Kadirov Extracurricular and optional activities in mathematics. - T: Teacher, 2000.
3. Abdurakhmanov A., Narmonov A., Normurodov N. History of mathematics. T.: UzRMU, 2004.
4. Yunusova D.I. Modern technologies of teaching mathematics, T.: 2007.
5. Jumayev M.E. Theory and methodology of development of mathematical

concepts in children. Tashkent. "Ilm Ziya" 2005.